

MOBILE PHONE DEVICE: EFFECTS ON STUDENTS' BEHAVIOR AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Mobile Phone Device: Effects on Students' Behavior and Academic Performance

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Abstract

This study was conducted to evaluate the Mobile Phone Device: Effects on the Students Behavior and Academic Performance in Dualing High School in the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study would like to find out the socio-demographic profile, as well the personal characteristics of Dualing High School students in terms of age, sex, and grade and section/strand affiliated. Secondly, determine the usage of mobile phone device among respondents. Third, to what extend is the level of the respondents in using mobile phone device in terms of research, communication, and leisure. Fourth, effects of mobile phone device on the behavior and academic performance of the respondents in terms of honesty, punctuality, respect, responsibility, and trust. Lastly, determine their final grade for three major subjects. This study used quantitative research and utilized descriptive survey design with 200 respondents. This study determine particularly the effects of mobile phone device on the behavior and academic performance of Dualing High School students using a self-made questionnaire. Stratified random sampling with equal allocation was used in determining the respondents of the study. Fifty (50) students from each year level of grade 9 – 12. The total respondents of this study were 200. Data analysis and interpretation was done using descriptive showed that majority of the respondents were female which is (64%) or 128, while only (36%) or 72 were male. Most of the respondents were 16 years old. Generally, the respondents used their mobile phone for messenger both at home and in school. They statistics such as weighted mean, frequency count and percentage. The results of the study spend daily for their mobile phone load per week with 70-90 pesos and used during weekdays 7-9 hours and more than 10 hours for weekends. Majority used their phones daily for research, messenger for communication and 7-9 hours for leisure. The effects of mobile phone device on their values in terms of honesty, punctuality, respect, responsibility, and trust were positive. Based on the findings, it is hereby recommended that the students must use their mobile phone device effectively in a nice way and for academic purposes; this is for other researchers, to explore other behavior and academic performance not included in this study; and, this research is for further study. The 21st century is the age of modern technologies where people must inevitably adapt digitally, specifically the use of mobile phone devices like laptop, cellphone and tablet in the field of work, business, and school.

Keywords: *mobile phone, behavior, performance, academic*

Introduction

The 21st century is the age of modern technologies where people must inevitably adapt digitally, specifically the use of mobile phone devices like laptop, cellphone and tablet in the field of work, business, and school. taught us, students in today's generation have changed dramatically, and they were no more system centered in terms of education. He went on to described how these "digital natives" are being exposed to more gadgets and technology than was ever thought possible (Prensky,2001).

Mobile phone devices are another way of which a child can learn through because nowadays mobile phone device are one part of child's life. Our students don't just want mobile phone; they really need it for their learning in educational purposes. In today's situation, we do have now different kinds of mobile phone devices like laptops, tablets, cellphones, camera phones, iPods and Android phones. They are classified as keypad mobile phones, touch screen mobile phones, thick and thin mobiles with a couple of sensor and light for convenience purposes. This mobile phone device contains applications, journals, news, and social media that can make one another connected. That's how it meets the demands of people.

Mobile phone has influence people's lives in many aspects including education, English Language Learning (ELL), and lifestyle (Kim et. Al, 2014). The introduction of online games has influenced the way of using the gadgets in times now. These have become a common place in the lives of young and young adults around the world, which can provide opportunities to learn and be exposed in socialization to other people. However, it is unclear what values these students might place on mobile phone devices in relation to personal behavior and their academic performance. With the rapid development in Information and communications Technologies (ICTs), various changes and influences have been made in terms of lifestyle, methods and learning process. Currently, mobile phone devices are utilized by millions of users, most of whom are students and adolescents, for variety of purposes (Frohbe, et al 2009).

Many different schools are moving forward on giving opportunity to students by using mobile phone devices. This is their means or making learning easy. Mobile phone devices offer teachers and students a more flexible approach to learning. Computer laboratory are great, but do your students use technology in the classroom, in the school garden, in the study hall, in the gym, and on field trips? With mobile phone devices, you can do all this, and more (Bauer, et al 2002).

The education system we work in is not always known for its speed at latching on to new ideas and methodologies, but with mobile phone devices it is catching up-quickly. The iPod Touch, laptop, cellphones, tablets for instance, were among the more popular mobile

learning devices to hit classrooms across the country. This tactile, touch-screen device is easy for children to use, and comes with built-in Wi-Fi to access the Internet. However, it also has the ability to tap into the thousands of apps available at the iTunes and Play Store. For Instance, you can use the dictionary and thesaurus on Dictionary.com, explore the world with Google Earth, or plot equations with Quick Graph, Download the Kindle app and turn your iPod into an e-reader Create your own stories with Story Kit, and find out about the latest space missions with the NASA app. These, and many others, are free downloads that are ideal for educators to use with their students in school (Capie shi, 2020)

Tenkely (2010), a K-5 Technology Integration Specialist and the author of the Learning Technology blog has recently submitted a proposal to use the iPod in a one-to-one learning environment at her elementary school. She said it was a great way to improve the reading, math, and science skills of the students at her school. It provides the potential to empower and uplift students in their leaning. She said the level of education in the 21st century; teachers have to be adoptive, innovative in accessing mobile phone devices. It helps students to solve different problems which maybe critical or physical.

Those were only uplifting the optimistic side of using mobile phone devices, but it also has the reasonable consequence or negative effects specifically in students' values such as honesty, punctuality, respect, responsibility and trust. This can also cause illness, laziness, addiction, and used as accessory to crimes. It can be a factor why students are unfocused on their studies, and their academic performance are being affected.

Research Questions

This study was conducted to evaluate the Mobile Phone Device: Effects on the Students Behavior and Academic Performance in Dualing High School in the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study aimed to determine:

1. What are the personal characteristics of Dualing High School students as respondents of this study, in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. grade and section/strand?
2. What are the students' responses to the following mobile phone devices-related questions, such as:
 - 2.1. particular program in their mobile phone they usually use;
 - 2.2. where they use mobile phone;
 - 2.3. how often they purchase load in a week;
 - 2.4. how much they spend load per week;
 - 2.5. how many hours they usually use their mobile phone during weekdays; and
 - 2.6. how many hours they usually use their mobile phone during weekends?
3. To what extent is the students' level of usage of mobile phone devices, in terms of:
 - 3.1. research;
 - 3.2. communication; and
 - 3.3. leisure?
4. What are the effects of mobile phone devices on the behavior of the students, in terms of:
 - 4.1. honesty;
 - 4.2. punctuality;
 - 4.3. respect;
 - 4.4. responsibility; and
 - 4.5. trust?
5. What is the academic performance of the students, in terms of:
 - 5.1. English;
 - 5.2. Science; and
 - 5.3. Mathematics?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the quantitative research and utilized descriptive survey design. This study determined particularly the effects of mobile phone device on the values of the Dualing High School students using a self-made questionnaire.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the two hundred (200) selected junior and senior high school students of Dualing High School who were currently enrolled for the School Year 2022-2023. Stratified random sampling with equal allocation of fifty (50) students was used in determining the respondents of the study. Fifty (50) students from each of the strands, specifically the Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Accountancy Business and Management (ABM), Information Computer Technology (ICT), and Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL). The total respondents of this study is 200 students.

Instrument

The research instrument used to elicit information from the respondents was a self-made survey questionnaire.

Part I determined the personal characteristics of the respondents.

Part II determined the respondent's usage of mobile phone devices and their academic performance in terms of the kind of application used, number of hours and amount of money spent during weekdays and weekends.

Lastly, Part III determined the effects of mobile phone device on the values of Dualing High School students.

Procedure

In collecting data about this study, the following procedure was done. First, a written permission to the head of the school through the principal was obtained before the administration of the survey. Second, the researcher explained first to the respondents the item before the distribution of the questionnaire to ensure that items were understood by the respondents. Third, the researcher collected, tallied, analyzed and interpreted the data.

Results and Discussion

This section presents and discusses the data obtained by the researcher about the effect of mobile phone device on students' behavior and academic performance.

Personal Characteristics of the Respondents

Table 1 was presented in tabular form the socio-demographic profile of the 200 students who are the respondents of this study. This profile is in terms of year and section/strand, age, and sex. Table 1 presents the personal characteristics of the respondents in terms of their year and section/strand S.Y 2022 - 2023.

Table 1. *Profile of the Respondents in terms of Grade Level, Section and Strand*

<i>Year & Section/Strand</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Grade 9 Quirino and Magsaysay	50	25%
Grade 10 Garcia and Marcos	50	25%
Grade 11 HUMSS (Aristotle) and 11 ABM (Edison)	50	25%
Grade 12 HUMSS (Euclid) and 12 ABM (Galilie)	50	25%
Total	200	100%

As indicated in Table 1, the respondents were selected from the Grades 9 to 12 with equal numbers and percentages. Twenty-five percent (25%) or fifty (50) respondents were from Grade 9, another twenty-five percent (25%) or 50 students were from Grade 10. Likewise, twenty-five percent (25%) or fifty (50) students were from Grade 11 and another twenty-five percent (25%) or fifty (50) students were from Grade 12. A total of two hundred (200) students were selected as respondents of the study.

Age Profile

Table 2 presents the personal characteristics of the respondents in terms of their age during S.Y 2022 - 2023.

Table 2. *Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
14	32	16%
15	50	25%
16	68	34%
17	40	20%
18	10	5%
Total	200	100%

The data in Table 2 show that the respondents belong to different ages. Ten (10) or five percent (5%) of them were 18 years old; forty (40) or twenty percent (20%) were 17 years old; sixty-eight (68) or thirty-four percent (34%) were 16 years old; fifty (50) or twenty-five percent (25%) were 15 years old, and thirty-two (32) or sixteen percent (16%) were 14 years old. It exhibits that most of the respondents were 16 years old.

Sex Profile

Table 3 presents the personal characteristics of the respondents in terms of their sex. Table 3 exhibits the profile of the respondents in terms of sex. It is shown the one hundred twenty-eight (128) or 64% of the respondents were female. On the other hand, seventy-two (72) or 36% of the respondents were male. To conclude, most of the respondents of this study were male.

Table 3. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	128	64%
Male	72	36%
Total	200	100%

Usage of Mobile Phone Device among Respondents

Table 4 shows the mobile phone applications that are commonly used by the respondents.

Table 4. Mobile Phone Applications that are Frequently used by the Respondents

Mobile Phone Applications	Frequency	Percentage
Youtube	30	15%
Google	0	0%
Tiktok	45	22.5%
Facebook	40	20%
Messenger	58	29%
Mobile Games	27	13.5%
Instagram	0	0%
Twitter	0	0%
Merriam Webster	0	0%
Total	200	100%

Table 4 shows the frequently used mobile phone applications. 58 or (29%) of the respondents were using Messenger, 45 or (22.5%) were using TikTok, 40 or (20%) were using Facebook, 30 or (15%) were using YouTube, 27 or (13.5%) were using Mobile Games, while none of them chose the following applications. Google, Twitter, and Merriam Webster Dictionary. It shows that most of the respondents chose Messenger as the mobile phone applications that is frequently used by them.

Table 5. Places Where the Respondents Use Mobile Phones

Places	Frequency	Percentage
At School	0	0%
At Home	0	0%
Both	200	100%
Others	0	0%
Total	200	100%

Table 5 indicates that all of the respondents or 100% used their mobile phone devices both in school and at home.

Table 6. Purchasing of Load for Mobile Phone Devices

Load Of Mobile Phone	Frequency	Percentage
Daily	135	67.5%
Once A Week	49	24.5%
Others	16	8%
Total	200	100%

Table 6 indicates the respondents on how they soften spent load for their mobile phone devices. There were one hundred thirty-five (135) or 67.5% who spend daily for their load, forty-nine (49) or 24.5% were saying once a week, and sixteen (16) or 8% spend load for twice a week, thrice a week, and once a month.

Table 7. Load Spent per Week for Mobile Phone Devices

Amount Spent For Mobile Phone Load	Frequency	Percentage
10 – 30 Pesos	21	10.5%
40 – 60 Pesos	49	24.5%
70 – 90 Pesos	120	60%
100 Pesos And Above	10	5%
Total	200	100%

Table 7 indicates the respondents how much do they spend for their mobile phone load per week. It is shown that one hundred twenty (120) or 60% spent 70 – 90 pesos, forty-nine (49) or 24.5% spent 40 – 60 pesos, twenty-one (21) or 10.5% spent 10 – 30 pesos, and only ten (10) or 5% said that they spent more than 100 pesos.

The table 8 indicates the respondents mostly consume 7 - 9 hours in using their mobile phones with one hundred seventy-five (175) or 87.5%, fifteen (15) or 7.5 of the respondents spent 4 – 6 hours, and ten (10) or 5% used 10 hours and above, while no one answered 1 – 3 hours.

Table 8. *Number of Hours Consumed in Using Mobile Phones during Weekdays*

Hours Consumed for Mobile Phone Usage during weekdays	Frequency	Percentage
1 – 3 hours	0	0%
4 – 6 hours	15	7.5%
7 – 9 hours	175	87.5%
10 hours and above	10	5%
Total	200	100%

As shown in table 9, one hundred fifty-five (155) or 77.5% of the respondents consumed 10 hours and above in using mobile phone during weekends, and the remaining forty-five (45) or 22.5% consumed only 7 – 9 hours.

Table 9. *Number of Hours Consumed in Using Mobile Phone during Weekends*

Hours Consumed for Mobile Phone Usage during Weekends	Frequency	Percentage
1 – 3 hours	0	0%
4 – 6 hours	0	0%
7 – 9 hours	45	22.5%
10 hours and above	155	77.5%
Total	200	100%

Mobile Phone Usage in Research, Communication, and Leisure

Table 10 - 13 mobile phone usage in research, communication, and leisure of Dualing High School students S.Y 2022 – 2023.

Table 10. *The Use of Mobile Phones for Research*

Research	Frequency	Percentage
Daily	140	70%
Once a week	60	30%
Others, please specify	0	0%
Total	200	100%

As shown in the table 10, 140 (70%) used their device daily for research and sixty (60) or 30% were using their device once a week.

Table 11. *The Use of Mobile Phones for Communication*

Communication	Frequency	Percentage
Messenger	200	100%
Calling	0	0%
Texting	0	0%
Others, please specify	0	0%
Total	200	100%

Table 11 shows all the respondents or (100%) were answered they used their device in terms of communication through messenger.

Table 12. *The Use of Mobile Phones for Leisure*

Leisure	Frequency	Percentage
1 – 3 hours	0	0%
4 -6 hours	25	12.5%
7 – 9 hours	120	60%
10 hours and above	55	27.5%
Total	200	100%

As indicated in the table, 120 (60%) spent 7 – 9 hours using their mobile phones for leisure, 55 (27.5%) spent 10 hours and above, and the remaining 25 (12.5%) spent 4 – 6 hours.

General Effects of Mobile Phone Usage on the Behavior and Academic Performance of the Students of Dualing High School.

Table 13-17 shows the effects of mobile phone device on the Behavior and Academic Performance of Dualing High School students S.Y 2022 – 2023 in terms of honesty, punctuality, respect, responsibility, and trust

Table 13 shows the effects of mobile phone device on the Behavior and Academic Performance in terms of honesty in Dualing High School students. Specifically, the respondents never lie about their whereabouts to their parents or guardian with a weighted mean of (3.84), they never used their mobile phone for cheating as “kodigo”, asking answers or etc., with a weighted mean of (3.67), they say the truth whether its good or bad for them or other people with a weighted mean of (3.42), they used it to show their real attitude/identity

with a weighted mean of (3.15), they express their thoughts and feelings, even if it may hurt other people with a weighted mean of (3.09), they avoid plagiarism in doing their research work with a weighted mean of (2.99), they used it to inform their parents about any payments in school with a weighted mean of (2.98), they used it to tell what their real problem is with a weighted mean of (2.90).

Table 13. *Effects of Mobile Phone Usage in terms of Honesty*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I say the truth whether it's good or bad for me or other people.	3.42	Positive
2. I express my thoughts and feelings, even if it may hurt other people.	3.09	Positive
3. I never lie about my whereabouts to my parents or guardian.	3.84	Positive
4. I avoid plagiarism in doing my research work.	2.99	Positive
5. I have never used my mobile phone for cheating as "kodigo", asking answers or etc.,	3.67	Positive
6. I use this to show my real attitude/identity.	3.15	Positive
7. I use it to tell what my real problem is.	2.90	Positive
8. I use it to inform my parents about any payments in school.	2.96	Positive
Overall Mean	3.25	Positive

Legend: 3.51–4.00 – Highly Positive; 2.51–3.50 – Positive; 1.51–2.50 – Negative; 1.00–1.50 – Highly Negative

Table 13 revealed the overall mean of (3.25) with a verbal description of "positive" which implies that the respondents were honest in using their mobile phone device.

The findings of this study supports Ferris (2016) who said that experts have determined that a person who buys and uses mobile phone devices were more humble and honest.

Table 13 shows the effects of mobile phone device on the Behavior and Academic Performance in terms of honesty in Dualing High School students as of the 1st and 2nd Quarter for the S.Y 2022 – 2023

Table 14. *Effects of Mobile Phone Usage in terms of Punctuality*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I use mobile phone as alarm to keep me punctual with my appointments.	3.65	Positive
2. I use mobile phone as reminders of important things to do in order not to miss deadlines.	3.25	Positive
3. I asked my contacts for important dates or events to attend to.	3.39	Positive
4. I used my mobile phone to keep me updated of the time.	3.26	Positive
5. I use it in constructing advance planning.	3.22	Positive
6. I used it to inform my contacts in advance about important things and events.	3.32	Positive
Overall Mean	3.35	Positive

Legend: 3.51–4.00 – Highly Positive; 2.51–3.50 – Positive; 1.51–2.50 – Negative; 1.00–1.50 – Highly Negative

Table 14 shows the effects of mobile phone device on the Behavior and Academic Performance in terms of punctuality in Dualing High School students. Specifically, they used mobile phone as alarm to keep them punctual with their appointments with a weighted mean of (3.65), they asked their contacts for important dates or events to attend to with a weighted mean of (3.39), they used it to inform their contacts in advance about important things and events with a weighted mean of (3.32). they used their mobile phone to keep me updated of the time with a weighted mean of (3.26), they used mobile phone as reminders of important things to do in order not to miss deadlines with a weighted mean of (3.25), they used it in constructing advance planning with a weighted mean of (3.22),

Table 14 revealed the overall mean of (3.35) with a verbal description of "positive" implies that the respondents used their mobile phone device to keep them punctual with the things that they do.

The findings of this study similar with Bicard and Lott et. al (2012) in their research shown that student who uses mobile phone devices the effects on their studies were positive and their individual attitude, good values of arriving on time, therefore they were enough considered as punctual.

Table 14 shows the effects of mobile phone device on the Behavior and Academic Performance in terms of punctuality in Dualing High School students as of the 1st and 2nd Quarter for the S.Y 2022 – 2023.

Table 15. *Effects of Mobile Phone Usage in terms of Respect*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I always pleasantries like good morning, hi and hello whenever I text.	3.46	Positive
2. I use "po" and "opo" when answering especially to elders.	3.75	Positive
3. I address Ma'am or Sir to people in authority.	3.65	Positive
4. I refrain from saying disrespectful words or bad words.	3.23	Positive
5. I show respect to other people regardless of race, religion, age, sex, and others.	3.18	Positive
6. I am courteous when dealing with other people.	3.15	Positive
Overall Mean	3.40	Positive

Legend: 3.51–4.00 – Highly Positive; 2.51–3.50 – Positive; 1.51–2.50 – Negative; 1.00–1.50 – Highly Negative

Table 15 shows the effects of mobile phone device on the Behavior and Academic Performance in terms of respect in Dualing High School students. Specifically, they used "po" and "opo" when answering especially to elders with a weighted mean of (3.74), they

address Ma'am or Sir to people in authority with a weighted mean of (3.65), they always pleasantries like good morning, hi and hello whenever I text with a weighted mean of (3.46), they refrain from saying disrespectful words or bad words with a weighted mean of (3.23), they show respect to other people regardless of race, religion, age, sex, and others with a weighted mean of (3.18), they were courteous when dealing with other people with a weighted mean of (3.15).

Table 15 revealed the overall mean of (3.40) with a verbal description of "positive" which implies that the respondents were respectful. The findings of this study supports with Kushlev (2017) a psychologist investigator that the values of student specifically those who uses mobile phones according to survey and examined that it has great impact on their attitude politically and sociability. Therefore they were considered as respectful enough.

Table 15 shows the effects of mobile phone device on the Behavior and Academic Performance in terms of respect in Dualing High School students as of the 1st and 2nd Quarter for the S.Y 2022 – 2023

Table 16. *Effects of Mobile Phone Usage in terms of Responsibilities*

Statements	Weighted Mean	Description
1. I keep myself updated the quizzes, projects, and reports I missed using my mobile phone.	3.61	Positive
2. I do my assignments, projects, and reports using mobile phone.	3.16	Positive
3. I don't forward or send unreliable information to others.	3.33	Positive
4. I refrain from watching obscene or indecent videos or movies which could be a bad influence to me.	3.23	Positive
5. I discipline myself from over-using my mobile phone which could affect my studies.	3.16	Positive
6. I used it for study purposes as well as in doing business.	3.33	Positive
7. I used it to improve my performance in school.	3.38	Positive
8. I use it to remind myself about personal obligations.	3.24	Positive
Overall Mean	3.30	Positive

Legend: 3.51–4.00 – Highly Positive; 2.51–3.50 – Positive; 1.51–2.50 – Negative; 1.00–1.50 – Highly Negative

Table 16 shows the effects of mobile phone device on the Behavior and Academic Performance in terms of responsibilities in Dualing High School students. Specifically, they keep themselves updated the quizzes, projects, and reports I missed using my mobile phone with a weighted mean of (3.61), they used it to improve my performance in school with a weighted mean of (3.38), they don't forward or send unreliable information to others with a weighted mean of (3.33), they used it for study purposes as well as in doing business with a weighted mean of (3.33), they refrain from watching obscene or indecent videos or movies which could be a bad influence to them with a weighted mean of (3.23), they use it to remind myself about personal obligations with a weighted mean of (3.24), they do their assignments, projects, and reports using mobile phone with a weighted mean of (3.16), they discipline myself from over-using my mobile phone which could affect my studies with a weighted mean of (3.16).

The overall mean is (3.30) with the verbal description "positive" and it implies that the respondents were responsible. The findings of this study similar with Caple (1996) further stated in his study that the group of students who received cellular phone messages were more inclined to study therefore improving their exam results as compared to those who were given printed handouts. The students who used mobile phone devices were proven more responsible in their studies.

Table 16 shows the effects of mobile phone device on the Behavior and Academic Performance in terms of responsibility in Dualing High School students as of the 1st and 2nd Quarter for the S.Y 2022 – 2023

Table 17. *Effects of Mobile Phone Usage in terms of Trust*

Statements	Weighted Mean	Description
1. I keep electronic conversation or message confidential.	3.63	Positive
2. I don't spread rumors or intrigues to other people.	3.20	Positive
Overall Mean	3.41	Positive

Legend: 3.51–4.00 – Highly Positive; 2.51–3.50 – Positive; 1.51–2.50 – Negative; 1.00–1.50 – Highly Negative

Table 17 shows the effects of mobile phone device on the Behavior and Academic Performance in terms of trust in Dualing High School students. Specifically, they keep electronic conversation or message confidential with a weighted mean of (3.63), with a verbal description of "positive" and they don't spread rumors or intrigues to other people with a weighted mean of (3.20). The overall mean of (3.41) with a verbal description of "positive" which states that Dualing High School students were trustworthy. The findings of the study in corroboration with Kushlev & Proulx (2016) persons who also used their mobile phone devices to access information's by the use of social media, they found that in reaching those facts on the internet in common the respondents foresee greater trust.

Table 17 shows the effects of mobile phone device on the Behavior and Academic Performance in terms of trust in Dualing High School students as of the 1st and 2nd Quarter for the S.Y 2022 – 2023

Academic Performance in English, Mathematics and Science

Table 18 shows the Academic Performance of the respondents in English, Mathematics and Science in Dualing High School students as of the 1st and 2nd Quarter for the S.Y 2022 – 2023.

Table 18. *Academic Performance of the Respondents in English, Mathematics and Science*

Subject	Weighted Mean	Description
1. English	86.70	Very Satisfactory
2. Mathematics	87.51	Very Satisfactory
3. Science	86.91	Very Satisfactory
Overall Mean	87.04	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 90–100 – Outstanding; 85–89 – Very Satisfactory; 80–84 – Satisfactory; 75–79 – Fairly Satisfactory; Below 75 – Did Not Meet Expectation

As shown in the table 18. The respondents have (86.70) total average grade in English (87.51) in Mathematics, and (86.91) in Science. The overall mean of (86.70) With a verbal description of “Very Satisfactory” which states that Dualing High School students were academically performing well.

Use of Mobile Phone Devices for Research and Academic Performance

Table 19 presents the use of mobile phone for research and students’ academic performance in English, Science, and Mathematics.

Table 19. *Mobile Phone Device Usage for Research and Students’ Academic Performance*

Frequency	English	Science	Mathematics	Mean	Description
Daily	88.75	89.62	87.51	88.62	Very Satisfactory
Once a Week	85.48	85.89	86.78	86.05	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 90–100 – Outstanding; 85–89 – Very Satisfactory; 80–84 – Satisfactory; 75–79 – Fairly Satisfactory; Below 75 – Did Not Meet Expectation

Table above shows the frequency in the use of mobile phone devices in research and students’ academic performance in three major subjects. In daily, a total of (89.62) for Science, (88.75) for English, and (87.51) for Mathematics. This indicates that the highest among major subjects in use of mobile phone device in research daily was Science. While, in once a week, a total of (86.78) for Mathematics, (85.89) for Science, (85.48) for English. This indicates that the highest among major subjects in use of mobile phone device in research once a week was Mathematics.

The table 19 revealed the overall mean of (88.62) which implies that the respondents use of mobile phone devices in research daily, and overall mean of (86.05) for once a week. With a verbal description of “Very Satisfactory” which states that Dualing High School students were academically performing well.

Table 20 presents the use of mobile phone in leisure and students’ academic performance in English, Science, and Mathematics.

Table 20. *Hours Spent on the Use of Mobile Phone Devices for Leisure and Students’ Academic Performance*

Hours Spent on the Use of Mobile Phone Devices in Leisure	English	Science	Mathematics	Mean	Description
4 to 6 hours	86.15	85.29	86.37	85.93	Very Satisfactory
7 to 9 hours	86.21	85.91	86.19	86.10	Very Satisfactory
10 hours and more	86.47	85.20	86.29	85.98	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 90–100 – Outstanding; 85–89 – Very Satisfactory; 80–84 – Satisfactory; 75–79 – Fairly Satisfactory; Below 75 – Did Not Meet Expectation

Table above shows the hours spent on the use of mobile phone devices in leisure and students’ academic performance in three major subjects. In 4 to 6 hours, a total of (86.37) for Mathematics, (86.15) for English, and (85.29) for Science. This indicates that the highest among major subjects in use of mobile phone device in leisure 4 to 6 hours was Science. And 7 to 9 hours, a total of (86.21) in English, (86.19) in Mathematics, and (85.91) in Science. This indicates that the highest among major subjects in use of mobile phone device in leisure 7 to 9 hours was English. While, in 10 hours and more, a total of (86.47) for English, (86.29) for Mathematics, and (85.20) for Science. This indicates that the highest among major subjects in use of mobile phone device in leisure 10 hours and more was English.

The table 20 revealed the overall mean of (85.93) in 4 to 6 hours, which implies that the respondents use of mobile phone devices in leisure. (86.10) in 7 to 9 hours, while (85.98) in 10 hours and more. With a verbal description of “Very Satisfactory” which states that Dualing High School students were academically performing well.

Table 21 presents the usage of mobile phone and students’ academic Performance in English, Science, and Mathematics.

Table 21. *Mobile Phone Devices Usage and Students’ Academic Performance*

Usage of Mobile Phone Devices	English	Science	Mathematics	Mean
Youtube	85.25	86.22	86.37	85.94
TikTok	85.57	86.23	86.19	85.99
Facebook	87.14	86.51	85.29	86.31
Messenger	87.21	86.34	87.34	86.96
Mobile Games	85.25	86.12	86.31	85.89

Legend: 90–100 – Outstanding; 85–89 – Very Satisfactory; 80–84 – Satisfactory; 75–79 – Fairly Satisfactory; Below 75 – Did Not Meet Expectation

Table above shows the usage of mobile phone devices in these major applications. In YouTube, (86.37) for Mathematics, (86.22) for Science, and (85.25) for English. In TikTok, (86.23) for Science, (86.19) for Mathematics, and (85.57) for English. In Facebook, (87.14) for English, (86.51) for Science, (85.29) for Mathematics. In Messenger, (87.34) for Mathematics, (87.21) for English, (86.34) for Science. While, in Mobile Games, (86.31) for Mathematics, (86.12) for Science, (85.25) for English. This indicates that the highest in usage of mobile phone devices among applications was Youtube, with the mean of (83.95), (83.00) in TikTok, (82.65) in Facebook, (82.96) in Messenger, (81.23) in Mobile Games.

The table 21 revealed that the highest in usage of mobile phone devices among applications was Youtube, with the mean of (85.94), (85.99) in TikTok, (86.31) in Facebook, (86.96) in Messenger, and (85.89) in Mobile Games. With a verbal description of “Very Satisfactory” which states that Dualing High School students were academically performing well.

Conclusions

The respondents used their mobile phone device for messenger both at school and home. They spent load daily and about 70 – 90 load per week. 7 – 9 hours consumed time per weekdays and 10 hours and above per weekends.

Mobile Phone Usage in Research, with 125 (62.5%) all the respondents or (100%) in terms of communication through messenger, and 120 (60%) were spent 7 – 9 for leisure.

The effects of mobile phone device on the honesty, punctuality, respect, responsibility and trust of Dualing High School students were positive.

The Academic Performance of the respondents in English with (86.70), Mathematics with (87.51) and Science with (86.91).

Recommendations

That the students must use their mobile phone device effectively in a nice way and for academic purposes.

This is for other researchers, to explore other behavior and academic performance not included in this study.

This research is for further study.

References

- Alizada, Masturah Pakbin, et al. “Educational Technology and Mobile Learning.” Strong Schools, Asian University for Women, 25 Jan. 2023, pressbooks.pub/schools/chapter/educational-technology-and-mobile-learning/.
- Ary D. Jacobs (2002) introduction o research in edcaion (6th ed). Belmon.
- Bauman, Z. (2005) Work, Consumerism and the New Poor. Berkshire: Open University Press. Bauman, Z. (2005) Work, Consumerism and the New Poor. Berkshire: Open University Press.
- Bauer, A.M. & Ulrich, M.E. (2002). I've got a palm in my pocket: using handheld computers in an inclusive classroom. Teach. Exceptional Children, 35(2), 18-22.
- Bauman, Z.(2003. Liquid love: On he frailty of hman bonds. Cambrige ,K: Polity Press.
- Bay Atlantic University April 2, et al. “Auditory Learner: Characteristics & Benefits.” Bay Atlantic University - Washington, D.C., 2 Apr. 2020, bau.edu/blog/auditory-learner/.
- BenMoussa, C. (May, 2003). Workers on the move: New opportunities through mobile commerce. Paper presented a he meeting of the Stockholm Mobility Routable, Stockholm, Sweden
- Behling, K., & Hart, D. (2008). Universal design: A model for professional development. In Universal design in higher education: From principles to practice (pp. 109–125). Cambridge, MA: Harvard Education Press.
- Capie shi, The Use and Effect of Smartphones in Students’ Learning ..., digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=6260&context=libphilprac. Accessed 15 Dec. 2024.
- Cooper, McNamee, Kai, and Mallory Yu. “50 Years Ago, Martin Cooper Made the First Cellphone Call.” NPR, NPR, 3 Apr. 2023.
- Digital Natives, Digital Immigrants - Marc Prensky, www.marcprensky.com/writing/Prensky - Digital Natives, Digital Immigrants - Part1.pdf. Accessed 15 Dec. 2024.
- Edwards, K., Newman, M., Sedivy, J., Smih . BalfanzD.,& Smeers D.K. (2002). Using spekaers for ad hoc peer-to-peer collaboration Paper presented a ACM 2002 Conference on Comer Supported Cooperaive Work (CSCW2002). Ne Orleans, Louisiana.
- Elder, Brooke. “What Is Tactile Learning? How Tactile Activities Improve Problem Solving & Language Processing.” Integrated Learning Strategies, 11 May 2016, [ilslearningcorner](http://ilslearningcorner.com).

- Frohberg, D., Goth, C., & Schwabe, G.(2009). Mobile learning projects a critical analysis of the 307e331.
- Fleming, N. D. & Mills, C. (1992). Not another inventory, rather a catalyst for reflection. *To Improve the Academy*, 11(1) 1992, 137-144.
- Flavin, Brianna. "Different Types of Learners: What College Students Should Know." Rasmussen University, 6 May 2019, www.rasmussen.edu/student-experience/college-life/most-common-types-of-learners/.
- Fogarty, G., Cretchley, P., Harman, C., Ellerton, N., & Konki, N. (2001). Validation of a questionnaire to measure mathematics confidence, computer confidence, and attitudes towards the use of technology for learning mathematics. *Mathematics Educational Research Journal*, 13, 154-160.
- Harvardgazette. "Experts See Pros and Cons to Allowing Cellphones in Class." *Harvard Gazette*, 29 Oct. 2024, news.harvard.edu/gazette/story/2023/03/experts-see-pros-and-cons-to-allowing-cellphones-in-class/.
- Huseyin Uzunboylu a, et al. "Using Mobile Learning to Increase Environmental Awareness." *Computers & Education*, Pergamon, 7 Nov. 2008
- Kinesthetic Learning Definition and Meaning." *Top Hat*, 16 Sept. 2019, tophat.com/glossary/k/kinesthetic-learning.
- Kolar, R.L., Sabatini, D.A. & Fink, L.D. (2002). Laptops in the classroom: do they make a difference. *J. Eng. Educ.*, 91, 397-401.
- Lawrence Kohlberg's Stages of Moral Development. *Encyclopædia Britannica*, Encyclopædia Britannica, inc., 28 Oct. 2024.
- Laura Silver, Aaron Smith. "2. Majorities Say Mobile Phones Are Good for Society, Even amid Concerns about Their Impact on Children." *Pew Research Center*, Pew Research Center, 7 Mar. 2019,
- New Jersey Bell, No. 1 Electronic Switching System (ESS), 144 Route 10 West, Succasunna, Morris County, NJ | Library of Congress,
- Nviri K. (2003). *Mobile communication: Essays on cognition and community*. Vienna: Passagen Verlag
- Qu, Ximei. "An Overview of Online Games and Their Effects on Adolescents." *SCIRP*, Scientific Research Publishing, 1 Nov. 2023
- Sloan, Douglas. (2008). "Progressive Education." *World Book Online Reference Center*.
- Tamim, R. M., Bernard, R.M., Borokhovski, E., Abrami P. C.,& Schmid, R.F. (2011). What forty years of research says about the impact of technology on learning:a second-order meta-analysis and validation study. *Review of Educational Research*,81,4e28.
- Tenkely ,Reimagining the Role of - Office of Educational Technology, tech.ed.gov/files/2017/01/NETP17.pdf. Accessed 15 Dec. 2024.
- Taylor, A. and Harper, R. (2001) 'The Gift of the Gab?: A Design Oriented Sociology of Young People's Use of the Mobile Phone', *Computer Supported Cooperative Work (CSCW)*
- Therrien, W. J. (2004). Fluency and comprehension gains as a result of repeated reading: A metaanalysis. *Remedial and special education*, 25(4), 252-261.
- Walker, J.W. (2001) *Zero Defections Human Resource Planning*, 24, 6-8. - References - Scientific Research Publishing.
- Wang, S.L.,& Wu, C.Y (2011). A application of context aware and personalized recommendation to implementation an adaptive ubiquitous learning system. *Expert Systems with Applications*.
- Winsler, A. & Manfra, L. (2002). Increasing student learning, technology use, and computer skills via use of WebCT in an undergraduate child development course: a pre and post course evaluation study. *Annual Conference of the American Psychological Association*, Chicago.
- Vavoula G.N. (2005). *D4:A Study of Mobile Learning Practices: International report of MOBILeran Project*.
- Verga, L., & Kotz, S. A. (2017). Help me if I can't: Social interaction effects in adult contextual word learning. *Cognition*, 16876-90. doi:10.1016/j.cognition.2017.06.018
- Vygotsky, L.S. (1978). *Mind in society: the development of higher psychological process*, Cambridge: Harvard university Press.
- Uzunboyl H. Cava, N. & Ercag, E.(2009). Using mobile learning to increase environmental awareness. *Computers & Education*, 52, 381-89.

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